

A Risk-aware Model for Task Planning in HRC

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Abstract—In this paper we propose a novel risk-aware model for human-robot coordination considering the main risk factors highlighted in international robotic standards. Namely, we propose to include multiple risk factors into a task sequencing model and use it for realizing a risk-aware task sequencing system based on a cutting-edge task planning framework. To assess our approach, we consider a realistic use case and evaluate the deployment of the task planner across various scenarios to show its efficacy and adaptability to diverse risk levels. Experimental results show a positive equilibrium between productivity and safety, achieving both high throughput and low operator risk.

Index Terms—Human-Robot Collaboration, Artificial Intelligence, Planning and Scheduling

I. INTRODUCTION

The use of cobots in manufacturing environments allows to automate challenging, hazardous, and repetitive tasks boosting the flexibility of manufacturing processes. Nevertheless, task coordination between humans and robots remains a critical issue for productivity. Human-Robot Collaboration (HRC) entails challenging safety issues as collaborative environments involve tight proximity between robots and human workers raising multiple challenges [4]. In order to endow cobots with the ability to quickly adapt their behaviors to the actual state of the environment and keep the user safe and engaged in the interaction, some human-aware task sequencing solutions have been proposed (e.g., [3]) where risk management is often not explicitly modeled. In this paper we propose a novel risk-aware model for human-robot coordination considering the main risk factors highlighted in international robotic standards (ISO 10218, ANSI-RIA R15.06-2012) to provide a more detailed representation of risks overcoming a flat description based on a single value expressing severity and probability, which may not capture the nuances hidden in a production scenario. Our model includes five flexible and general risk factors which can be applied to any HRC context. We also present a software prototype planner to reason over the different risk factors entailed by the execution of collaborative tasks and synthesize safe and efficient collaborative task plans. Specifically, we model HRC task assignment problems as human-aware task planning problems. A task planning system then generates task plans implementing sequences of actions to accomplish predefined production objectives [3]. This entails building a flexible temporal plan that transforms the initial state of a system into a desired goal state. AI planning

algorithms utilize domain knowledge and search techniques to efficiently explore the space of possible plans to identify the most feasible solution. This model informs a heuristic-based search that optimizes task assignment by considering a multi-objective perspective based on safety and efficiency. The designed heuristics allows the planner to find safe plans without compromising the efficiency of HRC productions. Its most important feature involves evaluating the risk of a situation by taking into account what robots and humans are doing at the same time. We evaluated our planner with other strategies in simulated environments demonstrating improved task assignments, effectively balancing safety and efficiency.

II. STATE OF THE ART

Standards for safety in HRC (e.g., ISO 10218) provides designers with appropriate guidelines to improve the safety of collaborative cells. On a robot control perspective, safety measures are to assign robot with tasks and controlling its motions to reduce the risk of collisions with the operator while keeping low cycle times. Task and motion planning solutions in HRC usually focus on general design issues or sub-problems such as scheduling human and robot actions, cooperative planning at a symbolic level, etc. (e.g., [1]). Several works investigated planning paradigms to enhance *human awareness* and realize effective and safe robot behaviors for HRC. In manufacturing, the main aim is to enforce productivity and guarantee good working conditions for operators, i.e., preserving safety and enhancing ergonomics of operators (e.g., [2]). Although existing works effectively address HRC issues, none of them rely on an explicit risk model supporting parameterized reasoning about safety. We propose a more specific risks model to foster more appropriate decisions.

III. A RISK AWARENESS MODEL FOR TASK SEQUENCING

We propose a model consisting of 5 risk factors describing the safety characteristics of HRC cells. The *intrinsic risk* value reflects the severity concept and indicates the inherent risk level of a specific task determined by properties independent of its execution method including, e.g., characteristics of the tool (e.g., with sharp or hot parts). The *geometry risk* depends on which trajectory the robot is following to carry out its task. The risk value of a trajectory is assigned based on how likely it is for that trajectory to intersect a human body part and which part it is likely to intersect. *Speed risk* is also a risk value, and it intuitively depends on how fast the robot is carrying out its task. *Collision risk* is a risk value that depends on how likely it is for the human and robot

to be in each other’s way. It mainly depends on the tasks being carried out by the human and the robot at the same time. This is a value that most closely translates to exposure. Impact probability is high not only if the human and the robot are close together but also when they accomplish a strictly collaborative task. The *human unpredictability* represents the concept of avoidance (along with geometry risk and movement speed). It is higher when the system is less certain about the human’s movement or intention. As an example, human unpredictability can encapsulate human expertise. When an operator is highly skilled we assume low uncertainty.

A heuristic function is defined on these risks factors whose values are determined by production engineers within $[0,1]$. A cobot can carry out a set of tasks A and the i -th task in A can be executed with a set of distinct trajectories T_i (each of them with its own risk factor $t_{i,j}$). Each trajectory T_i can be realized with different speed values $v_{i,j,k}$ from a set $V_{i,j}$. Each task in A has a set of tasks P_i that can be carried out concurrently by the human (each of those with its own risk factor $p_{i,n}$) and it also has its own level of intrinsic risk a_i . The operator is provided with an uncertainty values from a set U . Here, we assume that human uncertainty u depends exclusively on her expertise. To quantify a comprehensive risk value, we consider the cumulative risk formula: $R_{i,j,k,n} = a_i \cdot t_{i,j} \cdot v_{i,j,k} \cdot p_{i,n} \cdot u$. A task planner using $R_{i,j,k,n}$ can reduce the risk associated to the plan by, e.g. reallocating tasks, changing a motion trajectory, etc. Risk awareness at planning time can allow to generate plans with a lower risk of collisions and reduce the safety stops of the robot, greatly improving efficiency and safety.

IV. EXPERIMENTS AND EVALUATION

We realize a task planning system based on a framework already successfully applied in manufacturing scenarios [3], [5]. We implemented a *RiskAssessmentPlanner* with a customized search strategy determining the most promising and safe options to achieve production goals and applying a pareto optimization to balance between safety and efficiency [3]. We consider an experimental scenario inspired by an EU research project (<https://www.sharework-project.eu>) in which a human and a robot collaborate to build a mosaic [3]. The experiment considers a scenario based on a series of Pick-And-Place operations with a robot and a human collaborating to sort a set of cubes from a common working area into separated heaps, based on the cube’s material of different material, i.e., foam, wood, and hot metal cubes, with an increasing intrinsic risk. Each task can be carried out considering three different trajectories and with three increasing speed levels, influencing risk accordingly. And we consider human operator with two levels of experience (skilled or not skilled). For each task we defined a set of pre-compiled values associated to risks parameters representing an estimation of risk in the considered scenario.

To assess our search strategy, we implement other planners with different heuristics: giving priority to safety (*RiskSearchStrategy*), i.e., aiming to minimize safety and not performance; giving priority to makespan (*MakespanStrategy*), i.e., aiming to minimize makespan and not considering safety; a ”classical” depth-first strategy (*PlannerSearchStrategy*). We vary different

scenarios varying the amount of shared tasks between humans and robots and a different number of shared cubes. We consider human operators with high experience or with no experience. This allows us to see how the planners react to every combination of parameters. We consider several plan variations, each tested for all strategies and run 5 times per variation, for a total of 160 runs. Tests were performed on a workstation with a Ryzen 3600 CPU and 16 GB RAM.

Our approach enables the planner to make more informed decisions in task allocation and it consistently keeps the risk level low and, whenever possible, significantly enhances efficiency. Though our planner assigns tasks considering the assessed risk and, when feasible, it manages to reduce the risk of collisions. Finally, the planner provides a good trade-off between safety and efficiency reducing the risk of collisions and entailing the highest possible efficiency. The DFS Planner is the fastest as it is only concerned with plan suitability and is not aware of safety or efficiency. Other strategies have similar behavior with RiskPlanner being the one suffering the most from a higher amount of shared cubes. Indeed, a higher shared amount of boxes entails to work with a much higher branching factor taking more time to find a solution.

Fig. 1. Scatterplot of risk / makespan grouped by expertise / shared tasks

In Figure 1, the scatter plot illustrates how each strategy balances risk and efficiency. Data points are categorized by expertise and shared values. The significant aspect is the right side, indicating RiskAssessmentPlanner’s consistent superiority in safety over MakespanPlanner, while being faster than both Planner and RiskPlanner. For less experienced humans, RiskAssessmentPlanner acknowledges heightened risk, producing safer yet slower plans in response.

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